

Iodine Deficiency Disorders in Ruminants: A Mineral Deficiency in Limelight of Ruminant Medicine

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Mineral elements have an impact on animal growth, reproductive success, immunocompetence, and health concerns. They are components of several enzymes and help to coordinate a wide range of biological activities, hence they are critical to animal health and production. Optimal nutrition, with suitable trace mineral levels, ensures proper organ functioning, the most essential of which are structural, physiological, catalytic, and regulatory.

According to FAO/WHO animal health yearbooks, nutritional abnormalities account for 80 percent of animal diseases, with trace element deficiency accounting for more than half of them. Every year, occasional cases of mineral deficiency illnesses occur in developed nations with regular standards for maintaining nutritional profiles. Many mineral deficiency illnesses are sometimes missed in developing nations such as India, where undernutrition is largely focused on satisfying calorie, protein, calcium, phosphorus, and water demands.

Regardless of the fact that the importance of trace elements in animal and human health is well acknowledged, they are the most overlooked nutrients in animal diets. Their physiological importance is frequently underestimated, and their availability in suitable quantities in the feed is taken for granted. They are, nonetheless, required to sustain physiological function, optimise development and reproduction, activate immunological response, and so decide health status. Indeed, it is difficult to recognise the impact of trace mineral shortage since signs of deficiency or mineral imbalances are not usually obvious. A trace mineral shortage, on the other hand, can cause significant reductions in performance and output. Hence, trace minerals must be supplied to livestock in ideal concentrations and in accordance with changing requirements during the animal's fast growth and development as well as the production cycle.

Much work has been conducted in field of Clinical intervention nutrition to study role of various macro and micro mineral elements in interpretation of clinical conditions in animals. Among these minerals Iodine is one such which has sufficient scope in research due to several cases reported of its deficiency. Iodine (I) is one of seven well known micro minerals that dairy cattle and other animals require in their diets. In general, the thyroid gland of an animal accumulates more than 95 percent of total iodine. It is unique among minerals in that its deficiency causes a particular and easily identifiable thyroid gland enlargement known as goitre. Iodine's sole known metabolic functions are in the thyroid hormones thyroxine (T4) and triiodothyronine (T3), as well as the precursor iodothyronines. Both hormones have many activities in cell energy consumption, growth, as a transmitter of nerve impulses, and as a crucial element in brain development. Any deficiency of Iodine thus affects body metabolism in multitude causing various disorders. This deficiency can be more prone in Ruminants depending on their geographical area and managerial practices. This article hence focuses light on all aspects of Iodine deficiency disorders in Ruminants.

Different Iodine Deficiency Disorders in Ruminants- A Syndrome

1. Goitre- Hyperplasia of Thyroid Gland
2. Still Births, Perinatal Mortality, Weak Animals
3. Defective Ossification in Neonates
4. Abortions
5. Alopecia
6. Myxedema
7. Low Reproductive Performance

Etiology of Iodine Deficiency

Iodine deficiency can be a result of deficient iodine intake or secondarily conditioned by a high intake of calcium, diets consisting largely of *Brassica* spp., or gross bacterial pollution of feedstuffs or drinking water.

• Primary Deficiency-

1. As a result of a low iodine intake in the diet. Iodine needs are higher than what is available in the diet.
2. Feeding on low-iodine-content plants.
3. Feeding on plentiful pasture after heavy rains and a seasonal break produces clinical iodine deficit in newborn lambs due to low pasture iodine concentration.

- **Secondary Deficiency-**
 - a. Due to consumption of Goitrogenic Substances like
 1. Thiocyanates (formed by Cyanogenic Glycosides)- Cassava, Lisa Beans, Linseed, Sorghum, Sweet Potato, etc.
 2. Glucosinolates- Cabbage, Broccoli, Kale, Turnips, etc.
 3. Flavonoids- Soy, Millets, etc.
 4. Goitrin- Cabbage, Brussels, Sprouts, Rapeseed, etc.
 - b. High Calcium Intake
 - c. Consumption of fodder produced on soil that has been heavily contaminated with bacteria as a result of sewage.

Epidemiology

Iodine insufficiency is frequent in all species, although it is most prevalent in newborn animals. It is more frequent on landmasses that are continental in nature. An investigation of crossbred cows in Punjab, India, discovered that 36% of cows were iodine deficient, with significant geographic heterogeneity ranging from 0% to 86 percent within Punjab.

Risk Factors

- **Iodine Deficiency in Diet and Water**- Major source of Iodine is soil and drinking water. Iodine insufficiency is more frequent in areas where rainfall is intense and soil iodine is constantly lost by leaching.
- **Calcium-rich soil with a low humus content**- Iodine content is directly proportional to humus, but Ca containing soils are humus deficient and pose risk of Iodine deficiency.
- **Intake of goitrogenic substances**- Secondary deficiency occur due to ingestion of Goitrogenic Substances.
- **Severe bacterial pollution of drinking water** - Severe outbreak of Goitre is recorded from cattle running in pasture dressed with crude sewage as feeding of Sewage sludge is also linked to occurrence of goitre.
- **Characteristics of individual plant** - Different vegetations grown in same soil can also possess different amount of Iodine as it is also attributable to individual species characteristics.
- **Thyroid weight: Birth weight proportion**- Iodine deficiency is suspected if this ratio is more than 0.8g/kg in lambs.
- **Congenital**

Pathogenesis

Primary Deficiency:

1. A decrease in Iodine availability in the body leads to a decrease in Thyroxine synthesis.
2. Pituitary stimulation of Thyrotropic Hormone secretion
3. Thyroid tissue hyperplasia
4. Thyroid gland enlargement- goitre (involutes later to colloidal goitre)

Secondary Illness:

1. Consumption of goitrogenous substances
2. Liver detoxification and the formation of metabolites such as Thiocyanates and Sulfoyanates
3. Inhibit thyroid epithelial metabolic activity and iodine absorption
4. Thyroid Gland Enlargement- Goitre

Clinical Findings-

- The most visible sign of Iodine deficiency is goitre.
 - The most typical signs include a high incidence of stillbirths and weak babies.
 - Alopecia can be partial or complete.
 - Thyroid Gland Enlargement
 - Nervous tissue development in the foetus is reduced or incorrect.
1. **Cattle : Cardinal Manifestation-** Enlargement of Thyroid Gland
Weakness in Newborn Calves
 - Respiratory dyspnea
 - Lethargy, Weakness and difficulty in consuming colostrum. Partial alopecia is rare
 - Loss of libido in bull, failure to express estrus in cow and higher incidence of aborted stillborn or weak calves
 2. **Swine :** Characteristic findings are birth of hairless, stillborn or weak piglets often with Myxedema of skin of neck
 - Hairlessness is more marked on the limbs
 - Most affected piglets die within few hours of birth
 - Thyroid enlargement present but never cause visible swelling in live Pig
 - Survivors are lethargic, don't grow well, have waddling gait and legs weaknesses as a result of weakness of ligaments and joints.

3. **Sheep:** Adult Sheep in Iodine deficient areas can show high incidence of thyroid enlargement but are clinically normal, whereas, newborn lambs manifest weakness, extensive alopecia and palpable if not visible enlargement of thyroid gland.
 - Gestation length of ewes may be increased
 - There is increased peri-natal mortality especially in inclement weather
 - Marginal iodine deficiency can result in non-specific production losses from embryonic mortality or high perinatal lamb death and reduce growth rate.
4. **Goat :** Signs are same as that of sheep except that they are more severe in lambs.
 - Goat kids are goitrous and alopecic. The degree of alopecia varies from a complete absence of hair, through very fine hair to hair that is almost normal.

Clinical Pathology

Serum Iodine, T4 and T3 concentrations are biochemical markers of iodine metabolism that may precisely and reliably estimate the level of iodine in an animal's body, diagnose marginal insufficiency, and predict the response of a flock to iodine supplementation. Profiling **Selenium** and linked enzymes may be a diagnostic marker also a therapeutic area of research due to the strong interrelationship between iodine and selenium.

1. Laboratory assessment: Thyroid Stimulating Hormone (TSH) is useful in determining Iodine insufficiency in calves. TSH levels in goitrogenic calves are greater than in healthy calves. T4/T3, T4/TSH, rT3 & T3 concentrations and ratios are greater in healthy calves than in those with goitre. Calves with goitre that die have higher TSH values, lower T4, T3, T4/TSH & rT3 but similar T4/T3 ratio ($P > 1$) than Calves with goitre that live.

2. Thyroid weight: Birth weight Ratio: Non-Linear Relationship

- I. > 0.8 g/kg in lambs – Iodine Deficiency
- II. < 0.4 g/kg – Rarely deficiency of Iodine will be noticed

Necropsy Findings

1. Macroscopic enlargement of the thyroid gland, alopecia, and myxoedema.
2. Newborn lambs from ewes who were not given iodine had a thyroid weight to body weight ratio of 0.4g/kg or higher.
3. The gland in a calf with significant thyroid enlargement may weigh more than 20 grams.
4. Cattle and sheep birth values of 0.03 percent Iodine on a wet basis is deemed essential.

5. Histology- Glandular epithelial hyperplasia.
6. Hypoplastic hair follicles.
7. Osseo maturation is delayed.

Differential Diagnosis

1. Stillbirths- If a stillbirth occurs as a result of iodine deficiency, the gestation time is extended.
2. Thyroid hormone deficiency inherited.
3. Hyperplastic goitre with no gland enlargement—rare in ruminants.

Treatment

- When neonate epidemics arise, the focus is placed on supplying extra iodine to pregnant dams.
- Recommendations for control can be followed in therapy.
- Oral Administration- 280mg / head Potassium Iodide to pregnant ewes and provision of Iodized salt lick. Lambs- 20mg Potassium Iodide per os.
- Parenteral preparations of Iodine are also available that can be injected intramuscularly but they pose mainly prophylactic indication.

Control

Recommended Dietary intake of iodine for cattle is 0.8 to 1.2 mg/kg DM of feed for lactating and pregnant cows and 0.1-0.3 mg/kg DM of feed for non-pregnant cows and calves.

Various Control recommendations that can be followed to avoid iodine deficiencies are as follows-

1. Thyroid weight: lamb weight ratio should be monitored since a ratio larger than 0.8g/kg indicates iodine insufficiency.
2. Iodine preparations administered parenterally. Iodine (Iodized oil) IM injections three times at a dosage of 2370 mg iodine/dose at the start of lactation and at 100-day intervals, for example, increased iodine concentrations in milk to 58 micrograms/litre for at least 98 days following each treatment.
3. Oral administration of iodine in the form of salt or mineral blocks. It is recommended to add 200mg of Sodium Iodate per kilogram of salt or mineral block.
4. Iodine status should be checked on a regular basis if feedstuffs include goitrogenic substances.
5. A device that gradually delivers iodine into the forestomachs while remaining in situ has demonstrated good results in lowering congenital goitre in lambs when used in conjunction with other treatments.

6. Individual dose of 280mg potassium iodine or 370mg potassium iodate to ewes fed goitrogenic diet to prevent goitre development in lambs in the fourth and fifth months of pregnancy.
7. Tincture iodine within flank @4ml for cattle, 2ml for pigs and sheep
8. A 1ml iodine injection in poppy seed containing 40% bound iodine given 7-9 weeks before lambing to reduce lamb mortality.

Understanding Iodine deficiency disorders indeed gives a clinician to look towards certain clinical conditions that are otherwise not managed and diagnosed considering routine incidence of cases. Much research is still needed to find ways through which these conditions can be totally eliminated before they give rise to an outbreak. A farm can be protected from huge economic debts if proper prophylactic measures and necessary treatment approaches are implied to treat mineral deficiencies like that of IODINE.